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PERCEPTIONS AND KNOWLEDGE OF SECONDARY EDUCATION TEACHERS CYPRUS FOR EPILEPSY AND THE ETHICAL DIMENSION OF THE MATTER

Epilepsy is a neurological disorder with a serious impact on the quality of life of the individual, while many times its social consequences are much more serious than its nature itself. The present study aims to examine the perceptions and knowledge of secondary education teachers in Cyprus, as a first approach to the issue in the context of a broader research. The teachers responded to a questionnaire based on the ATPE (Attitudes Towards Persons with Epilepsy) and the data analysis includes t-test for independent samples and one-way analysis of variance. According to the results, there are serious misconceptions about epilepsy and large gaps in information and education, while ethical issues in education are also raised.

Keywords:epilepsy, knowledge, perceptions, teachers, ethics

Introduction

Epilepsy is a chronic brain disorder characterized by sudden and highly abnormal discharges of brain neurons. This leads to immediate disturbance of the senses, loss of consciousness, convulsions, or a combination thereof. According to the World Health Organization (2005), it is a medical and social condition-disorder or a group of

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disorders, with unique characteristics. Epilepsy is an ancient disorder, which goes back to the earliest written sources of humanity.

According to data, approximately 9 out of 1000 people suffer from epilepsy in the the European Union, while in underdeveloped countries, the number may be higher (WHO, 2005). More than 45 000 cases of children are diagnosed each year, while one in ten people will have at least one seizure in their lifetime. According to the Cyprus Epilepsy Support Association, there are approximately 8000 patients with epilepsy in Cyprus, while 2500 of them suffer from the drug-resistant form of the disorder.

Epilepsy carries a very strong social stigma (Thacker et al.2007). In fact, many times the stigma of epilepsy is worse and affects the psyche to a greater extent than the disorder (Mc Lin et al, 1995), while research shows that the psychosocial consequences of epilepsy are more serious than the disorder (Pal, 2003). Therefore, the way we treat people with epilepsy can deeply affect the individual and their quality of life and disrupt their daily life. In the case of children, this daily life also includes school.

It is a fact that the stigma that a disorder brings may not be related so much to its characteristics but more to the social stereotypes that are created due to ignorance, misconceptions and fears that come from and feed on them. It is also a fact that many of these perceptions may not be entirely misconceptions, but when they become stereotypes they lead to prejudices, raising (also) ethical issues.

This research is part of a broader and more complex study on chronic illnesses in Cyprus. It is a first approach of the subject and a contribution to filling the gap that exists regarding the study of epilepsy and chronic illnesses from a social and psychological perspective. Indeed, this matter has only been approached superficially in Cyprus before, while little is known about teachers'

perceptions towards people with epilepsy (and by extension their students).

Methodology

The survey involved teachers appointed to a public secondary school, regardless of their subject specialty. In the free area of Famagusta and according to the official data, there are approximately 410 teachers of every specialty, experience and level of study. These teachers come from various towns and villages in Cyprus and these data serves the survey to a very large extent. It is emphasized that at this stage, no strict representation of the general population of appointed secondary school teachers in Cyprus has been sought, but only a satisfactory sample for a first investigation of the matter within the framework of a larger survey.

The final sample of the survey consisted of 148 teachers from secondary schools in the Famagusta district. Of the 148 individuals, 51 (34.5%) were male and 97 (65.5%) were female. 84.5% (125 individuals) were appointed to a high school, while 15.5% (23 individuals) were appointed to a high school and their specialties were: General education (80.4%, 119 individuals), special education (4.7%, 7 individuals) and physical education (14.9%, 22 individuals). Years of service ranged from 1 year to over 21. Table 1 presents the demographic data of the sample.

The instrument used is a questionnaire based on the Perceptions of People with Epilepsy Scale (PPE), which was designed and developed by Richard F. Antonak. It is a relatively simple, easy-to-complete and tested instrument, the purpose of which is to measure knowledge and perceptions towards people with epilepsy. The questionnaire administered consisted of 28 translated and adapted items, of which 17 concern perceptions (Q1-3, Q5-9, Q11-15, Q17-21, Q24-25, Q27) and 7 knowledge (Q3-4, Q7, Q10, Q13, Q16, Q18, Q22-23, Q26,

Q28). Four items are common and concern both perceptions and knowledge (Q3, Q7, Q13, Q18) regarding people with epilepsy. Eight questions from the set concern children with epilepsy exclusively and are the ones that present particular interest for the present study (Q1, Q8, Q12, Q14, Q15, Q23, Q25, Q27) and are included in Table 4. Participants were asked to place themselves on a 6-point scale, which ranged from *I totally disagree* up to *I totally agree*. The teachers' responses were evaluated as positive or negative based on their placements on the scale and the content of the items and are summarized in tables.

Table 1. Demographic data of the sample (N=148)

Πίνακας 1. Δημογραφικά στοιχεία του δείγματος (N=148)

Φύλο	N	%
M	51	34,5
F	97	65,5
Σχολ. Βαθμ.		
Λυκ.	125	84,5
Γυμν.	23	15,5
Ειδικ.		
Γ.Ε	119	80,4
Ε.Ε.	7	4,7
Φ.Α.	22	14,9
Σχολ.Εμπ.		
1-5	22	14,9
6-10	18	12,2
11-20	65	43,9
21+	43	29,9

The questionnaires were distributed to the teachers and the offices of the assistant principals, explaining the requirements for the research and placing a collecting box in each place, where the participants returned the completed questionnaires. The secretarial staff of the schools provided the researcher with a general list of teachers, so that he would know how many teachers were in each

school and how many questionnaires should be distributed in each case for the research.

Results

Teachers' perceptions of children with epilepsy

Table 2 presents a summary and percentages of the positive or negative perceptions of teachers regarding people with epilepsy, of which items Q1, Q8, Q12, Q14, Q15, Q25 and Q27 clearly concern the *children* with epilepsy. When asked whether schools should place children with epilepsy in regular classes (Q1), teachers present a strongly negative perception, arguing for the opposite, although they believe that people with epilepsy should go to regular schools (Q8).

A percentage of 20.4% of teachers believe that the education of children with epilepsy does not concern the community (Q12), in contrast to 69.6% who consider the education of these children to be the responsibility of the community.

Table 2. Teachers' perceptions for people with epilepsy.

	N	+(%)	- (%)		N	+(%)	- (%)
Q1	148	0	100	Q14	148	0	100
Q2	148	100	0	Q15	148	87,2	12,8
Q3	148	74,3	25,6	Q17	148	0	100
Q5	148	100	0	Q18	148	100	0
Q6	148	100	0	Q19	148	85,1	14,9
Q7	148	0	100	Q20	148	0	100
Q8	148	100	0	Q21	148	100	0
Q9	148	0	100	Q24	148	0	100
Q11	148	0	100	Q25	148	0	100
Q12	148	69,6	20,4	Q27	148	0	100
Q13	148	0	100				

When asked whether children should be protected from their classmates with epilepsy (Q14), all participants agree that they should. The same perception/attitude is also present when asked whether children with epilepsy in regular classes have a negative impact on other children (Q27), where again everyone agrees that this is actually the case.

Regarding the statement that parents of children with epilepsy should expect from them what they expect from other children (Q15), 87.2% have a positive perception, while 12.8% have a negative one.

Finally, participants argue that families of children with epilepsy should not receive support from social welfare services (Q25), perhaps because they do not consider epilepsy to be a particularly serious illness.

Teachers' knowledge about people with epilepsy

Regarding the teachers' knowledge about people with epilepsy, this is summarized in Table 3 as positive or negative, depending on the statements and content of the questionnaire items. Some statements about epilepsy are of particular interest and these have been selected for reference and discussion.

Table 3. Teachers' knowledge for people with epilepsy.

	N	+(%)	-(%)		N	+(%)	-(%)
Q3	148	74,4	25,6	Q18	148	100	0
Q4	148	0	100	Q22	148	0	100
Q7	148	0	100	Q23	148	77	23
Q10	148	0	100	Q26	148	100	0
Q13	148	0	100	Q28	148	77,1	22,9
Q16	148	27,7	72,3				

The 100% of the survey participants believe that people with epilepsy do not have the usual life expectancy (Q4), a belief that is directly related to the belief that it is expected that the condition of the person with epilepsy will worsen over time (Q22).

There is complete agreement on the statement that people with epilepsy should be banned from driving (Q7) and it is related to the idea that people with epilepsy are prone to accidents (Q13). It seems that the belief that people with epilepsy are also mentally retarded (Q10) influences judgment and attitudes about the disease, to the extent that 100% of respondents believe that people with epilepsy are more likely to develop and manifest criminal tendencies (Q17) or that people with epilepsy are a danger to the public (Q11).

Independent samples t-test and one-way analysis of variance

Three independent samples T-tests were conducted to examine whether there are any statistically significant differences in the mean values between genders and years of experience of teachers, regarding their perceptions and knowledge about people with epilepsy. According to the results, a statistically significant difference in gender exists in items Q2, where $t(146) = -2.787$, $p=0.006$, Q6 where $t(146) = -2.454$, $p=0.015$, Q13 where $t(146) = 3.178$, $p=0.002$ and Q18 where $t(146) = -2.115$, $p=0.036$. The averages of the two genders for each subject are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Group Statistics

	Sex	N	Mean
Q2	male	51	5.6078
	woman	97	5.8144
Q6	male	51	5.6078
	woman	97	5.7938
Q13	male	51	4.8627
	woman	97	4.5155
Q18	male	51	5.6471
	woman	97	5.8041

Regarding the teachers' experience, the years of service were converted and separated into two groups: the first group includes teachers who have completed a decade in education and the second group includes teachers who have more than a decade of service in education. The separation into these two groups was not made arbitrarily, since a decade in education is considered a cut-off point for the teacher's experience. A statistically significant difference between the averages concerning the teachers' experience it seems to exist in the items Q5 where $t(146) = 2.171$, $p=0.032$, Q9 where $t(146) = 2.318$, $p=0.022$, Q19 where $t(146) = 2.193$, $p=0.030$ and Q27 where $t(146) = -2.028$, $p=0.044$. The averages of the two groups are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Group Statistics

	T	EXP.	N	Mean
Q5	1-10	40		5.775
	11+	108		5.5833
Q9	1-10	40		5.85
	11+	108		5.6574
Q19	1-10	40		5.65
	11+	108		5.2778
Q27	1-10	40		5.675
	11+	108		5.8426

In addition to the independent samples t-test, a test was also conducted to determine whether there was a statistically significant effect of specialization on teachers' perceptions and knowledge regarding people with epilepsy. The results of the one-way ANOVA showed that:

There is a statistically significant effect of specialization on variable Q2 (people with epilepsy have the same rights as all

people), where $F(2,145)=7.102$, $p=0.001$, with the difference focusing between general and special education.

There is a statistically significant effect of specialization on variable Q10 (people with epilepsy are also mentally retarded), where $F(2,145)=4.048$, $p=0.019$, with the difference focusing between general and special education.

There is a statistically significant effect of specialization on variable Q26 (children with epilepsy who attend regular classes have a negative effect on other children), where $F(2,145)=9.946$, $p=0.000$, with the difference focusing between general and special education.

There is a statistically significant effect of specialization on the variable Q28 (people with epilepsy can cope with the usual 40-hour workweek), where $F(2,145)=4.268$, $p=0.016$, with the difference focusing between general education and physical education.

Discussion

Some research shows that there is a more positive attitude towards people with epilepsy than in the past. Certainly, easier access to education, the development and dissemination of technology and through this knowledge and information play an important role in this. Of course, the level and extent of this change is not easy to determine, but the essence is that there is a positive change.

This paper constitutes a first approach of the perceptions and knowledge of secondary school teachers in Cyprus regarding epilepsy, as a small part of a more extensive study of the matter. Its usefulness concerns not only outreach and information purposes but can also serve the more general reflection on ethics and work ethics, as well as the design of information programs regarding epilepsy and other chronic illnesses that carry the same stigma.

Some of the research findings are particularly striking, mainly due to their strongly negative dimension. For example, the participants believe that people with epilepsy are also mentally retarded, that people with epilepsy are more likely to develop and manifest criminal tendencies, or that they are a danger to the public. In addition, the view that these people should go to regular schools but not be in regular classes, while other children should be protected from their classmates with epilepsy and that they are negatively influenced by them, is at least shocking.

These findings not only indicate the existence of serious misconceptions and large gaps in teachers' knowledge about epilepsy, but also a particularly negative attitude towards people with epilepsy, an attitude which obviously stems from these misconceptions and ignorance, as other research has also indicated (Diamantopoulos et al., 2006; Kobau & Price, 2003; Jacoby et al., 2004).

What is particularly important, however, is the subject matter of the study, which, in combination with other international research on the subject of epilepsy and chronic diseases, as well as the knowledge and perceptions of teachers, raises an additional issue: that of ethics. Specifically, it is obvious that there are large gaps in information and education, while any misconceptions lead to very serious prejudices. Therefore, ethical issues arise in school and in the way of dealing with and the management of children with epilepsy.

At the level of moral philosophy, issues of ethics in the workplace have been and are being discussed in depth in most advanced countries of the world. However, it is obvious that when it comes to school, issues of ethics in the workplace are not only raised for teachers but also for the children.

Beyond the technical aspect of work ethics, which concerns employer-employee, supervisor-subordinate and colleague-employee relationships, there is another aspect of work ethics. It concerns the ethics of *in the* work, where the two factors are not directly related

but indirectly and concerns the teacher-student relationship. This ethics concerns the ethics of humanistic education, which dictates the ethical principles that should govern this relationship that takes place in the workplace of the former.

Regarding the case of epilepsy and chronic illnesses of school children in general, we can say that the research that has been conducted so far demonstrates the existence of ignorance and prejudice to a large extent against these children. Even if it is involuntary or simply prejudices that stem precisely from ignorance and not from the personal worldview and philosophy of each individual, it still constitutes indirect discrimination against these individuals. It is therefore necessary to further investigate the matter of children with chronic illnesses in schools, as a primarily humanitarian issue, and to immediately promote information and support programs for both teachers and these children. Ultimately, it is a matter of ethics.

Restrictions

Among the positive aspects of the process, it is worth mentioning the achievement of a very satisfactory number of participants in this way, while among the limitations, the fact that some teachers were absent from the school or it was not possible to locate them within the school premises, as a result of which they did not have the opportunity to participate in the process. Regarding the limitations of the research, these focus first on the nature of the matter, which is a particularly delicate issue that is extremely difficult to measure, and then on the matter of sample size and sampling. Of course, it should be noted that a representative sample was not sought, since this is a first approach to the matter within the framework of a broader and

more complex research, with the sole purpose of a first idea of the current situation in schools.

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